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Annotation: This article describes the application of digital technology in the banking industry, the changes from its history to the present. In the course of the article, digital technologies in the field of banking are studied in three periods, ie three wave periods. We have learned the history of development in this area and the facts of what our modern banking system has gone through.

Keywords: incrementalists, corporate innovation, ATM, NetBank, DBF.

Digital technologies have been used in the banking industry for years. They are added in addition to existing operations or as a small extension. We call them “incrementalists” or first wave companies.

In the mid-1970s, Citi began experimenting with automated cash registers (ATMs). Former MIT chairman John Reed has revolutionized retail banking, leading Citi’s efforts in this area. The story of the ATM is an important study in the field of corporate innovation. The concept was simple: launch machines that could process transactions, such as cash withdrawals and deposit checks. What was revolutionary happened after that. Banks have historically had limited working hours, such as 9:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m., which was inconvenient for people who worked from 9:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.

However, in the 1950s, most households in the United States had a single income earner, and a stay-at-home wife was able to meet her banking needs during

the day. Mapping changes in society, with more and more women entering the workforce, the United States has seen an increase in two-income households, and therefore fewer people have access to daytime banking services. Thanks to e-banking, executives could see exactly when people were using banking services. The use of ATMs in the evening has increased. Banks, in turn, began extending their hours until late in the evening to accommodate a working specialist. By 2014, there were 524,000 ATMs in the United States, up from 484,000 in 1985.

Similar online banking was tested by Citibank and Chemical Bank in the 1980s through Minitel (France) and Prestel (UK), but did not develop until the 1990s with the growth of internet use. Simple browser-based tools have allowed consumers to access many basic banking transactions, such as money transfers, bank transfers, and electronic accounts. While existing commercial banks were originally providers of online banking, the rise of the internet also marked the emergence of internet banking - the most popular being NetBank in 1996.

We call second-wave companies like NetBank “digital hybrids”. By frequently using front-end systems to better market and connect with consumers, they are connected to older back and middle office infrastructure, risk modeling systems, and sometimes labor models. Often this will be the operating bank as the backbone of the hybrid banks.

For example, Simple Bank, founded in 2009, has introduced many innovations to simplify account management and costs, but uses Bancorp as a backup. Other emerging hybrid banks, such as Fidor Bank (Germany), Atom Bank (UK), LHV Pank (Estonia) and DBS Digibank (Singapore), have targeted IT infrastructure that is 60-80% cheaper to build and 30-50 percent cheaper than keeping old banks. The number of employees is also much lower, which is 10-15 percent of the traditional bank rate. However, these digital hybrids still use centralized databases, cloud-based storage, and primitive user data protocols. They represent a bridge solution between yesterday’s Main Street Bank and the full digital bank of the future.

A new set of technologies is emerging that will help consumers integrate more closely into their lives. These technologies promise financial services to consumers who do not work in 2.5 billion banks globally or do not have a full bank. They also offer more financial flexibility to more than 45 million small and medium-sized businesses worldwide.

DBFs use these technologies and are developed to meet the needs of the digital indigenous population - a crowd of people under the age of fifty who have grown up with computers as part of their daily lives. The first mobile strategy for millennia will provide easy access and quick adoption through continuous integration with their lives.

By adopting an advanced approach to data security, DBF will abandon an easily attacked central data warehouse in favor of a secure, encrypted, distributed data system. Personal data stores provide not only good digital wallets, but also the security of personal biometric data, which is an integral part of digital banking security protocols.

The new technology paradigm raises the question: what role do banks really play in the new world? Have we reached the end of the banks as we know them? Could the introduction of government-issued digital cash, which can be kept in the last leg of fractional banking and in a digital wallet outside the banking system, put the final nail in his coffin? We will now look at the basic requirements for a digital bank from three perspectives: the customer, the investor, and the bank itself.

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